

HISTORY AND CURRENT STATUS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATURAL SCIENCE TEACHING METHODOLOGY

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the history of the development of natural science teaching methods, their main stages, and their current status in relation to modern requirements. It provides information about the historical context of natural science teaching, and how it has changed since ancient times and in modern education systems.

Key words: Natural science, history of development, pedagogical technologies, ancient cultures, the era of renewal, nature conservation, prospects for education.

Introduction

The history of the development of natural science teaching methods dates back to ancient times. In the early days, people sought to make a living by observing nature and studying its laws. In the Middle Ages, with the development of science and the education system, interest in natural science increased. During the period of modernization, methods of teaching natural science were improved based on scientific methodologies and experiments.

Discussion

The natural and scientific views of the peoples of Central Asia developed in the 12th century. Such great minds as Al-Khwarizmi, Al-Farghani, Al-Farabi, Al-Biruni, Ibn, Sina, Z.M. Babur made a great contribution to this field.

Musa ibn Muhammad al-Khwarizmi (780-850)'s natural and scientific and mathematical works are of great value. He is the founder of algebra. He developed this science to the end. His works on natural science include "*Abridged Sindi Hindu*", "*Trigonometric Tables*", "*Treatise on Sundials*", and "*Surat Yer*". Al-Khwarizmi was the initiator of the development of the method of calculation and numerical relations in the study of natural processes. In his work on geography "*Kitabi Surat al-Arz*", he compiled maps showing the inhabited areas of the Earth and substantiated the forms of longitude and equivalence (coordinates) of each place. Therefore, the first half of the 9th century was called the Khorezmian period in science.¹

¹ https://recessans-edu.uz/files/books/2024-12-16-08-32-33_8c11df42a5b7e0a8faff305f07ae6467.pdf

Ahmad al-Farghani was one of the major figures of the Central Asian Renaissance. He was a man of encyclopedic knowledge and gained great fame not only in the East, but also in Europe in the fields of scientific astronomy, geography, mathematics and other natural sciences. In 812, A. Ferghani predicted a solar eclipse. A. Ferghani emphasizes that the Earth is not very large compared to the diameter of the sky. In his opinion, the globe resembles a point. The movement of the sky is two-sided, consisting of the movement of the entire dome of the universe and the movement of the planets. They are opposite in their directions, and their axes of rotation (and poles) do not coincide with each other.

The famous thinker Abu Nasr al-Farabi (870-950) expressed valuable ideas in his works, expressing his views on natural science. In his works such as *"The Structure of Human Organs"*, *"On the Organs of Animals and Their Functions"*, he gives an understanding of the structure, properties, functions, and similarities and differences of human and animal organs. He explains the interrelationship of human organs, the changes that occur in them, and the diseases that result from the violation of dietary habits. He emphasizes that humans have a great influence on nature.

Abu Rayhan Beruni (973-1048) describes the phenomena in the universe with the laws of development, and the phenomena on earth with the influence of the sun. In his opinion, man can scientifically study the existence of nature correctly. According to Beruni, the necessary opportunities for the survival of plants and animals on earth are limited, but plants and animals strive and struggle to reproduce endlessly. *"The world is filled with crops and offspring."* Beruni provided a lot of scientific information about the life, distribution, and importance of plants and animals. In his work *"Saydana"* he described 1116 types of medicines. He showed that 750 of them were obtained from plants, 101 from animals, and 107 from minerals. In his works *"Monuments of Ancient Generations"*, *"India"* interesting information is given about the structure of plants and animals, their interaction with the external environment.

Abu Ali Ibn Sina (980-1037) wrote more than 450 works. An encyclopedist scientist. *"The Canons of Medicine"* is considered a masterpiece in medical science. His advice on maintaining human health, dietary hygiene, recommendations for physical exercises, nervous diseases and their treatment, the influence of the external environment on a person, the transmission of all diseases through water and air, infectious diseases, etc. Along with medicine, he

made a great contribution to the development of knowledge about anatomy, psychology, surgery, hygiene and geology.²

Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur (1483-1530) was a poet, military leader, king, historian, gardener and naturalist. His works are a great treasure, the "*Baburnama*" is his greatest work. In this work, he widely interpreted knowledge about nature and geography. He provides invaluable information about the geographical location, climate, healing places, flora and fauna, and fossils of the region. Babur especially attached special importance to the cultivation of flowers, ornamental and fruit trees. He noted that the abundance of antelopes, mountain sheep, birds of prey in the Fergana Valley, gazelles in Samarkand, deer, mountain goats, partridges in Bukhara, and elephants, rhinoceroses, and monkeys in India is associated with specific conditions for their existence. Babur repeatedly observed earthquakes, lunar and solar eclipses, and considered them natural phenomena, laws of nature. The discipline of natural science teaching methodology has a 2-century history.

Conclusion

In general, in recent years, much attention has been paid to improving the content and essence of the subject of natural science. Along with these changes, the issue of changing the scientific-theoretical, pedagogical-psychological foundations of natural science teaching methods, as well as the directions of educational processes in accordance with the needs of the time, is also being identified as an urgent issue. After all, new approaches to the forms and methods of education used in the process of acquiring methodological knowledge in higher education institutions, that is, issues of increasing the effectiveness of education based on the use of pedagogical technologies, are envisaged.

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² https://renessans-edu.uz/files/books/2024-12-16-08-32-33_8c11df42a5b7e0a8faff305f07ae6467.pdf

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